

Figure S1. Different stages of jojoba germination and post-germinative growth. Scale bar, 1.0 cm.

Figure S2. Changes in starch and glucose content in germinating jojoba seeds. Data represent the mean of four biological replicates (accession 147) and error bars show standard deviation.

Figure S3. Immunoblot analysis of oleosin content in the microsomal fractions isolated from jojoba seeds (accession 147) at different stages of germination. A. M1: protein marker, M2: oleosins from maize, M3: oleosins from oat, seed: total protein extract from mature jojoba seeds, LD fraction: lipid droplet (wax body) fraction isolated from mature jojoba seeds. Numbers to the left indicate the positions of molecular mass markers. The black arrows indicate two isoforms of the maize oleosins. The blue arrows indicate two isoform of the jojoba oleosins (app. 17 kDa and 19.5 kDa). B. The original uncropped version.

Figure S4. Time course of TAG hydrolysis in phosphate buffer and HEPES buffer. Data represent mean values and error bars show the range of duplicates. Assay condition: aliquots (2.5 nmol of endogenous PC) of microsomal fraction mixture isolated from two individual jojoba seeds from each accession (35 dp); 20 nmol of [^{14}C]18:1-TAG added to freeze-dried microsomes in 19 μl benzene; benzene evaporation, and addition of 100 μl 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) or 0.1 M HEPES buffer (pH 7.); incubation at 60°C.

Figure S5. The effect of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ on the jojoba seed lipase activity towards 18:1-TAG.

Data represent mean values and error bars show the range of duplicates. Assay condition: aliquots (2.5 nmol of endogenous PC) of microsomal fraction mixture isolated from two individual jojoba seeds from each accession (35 dpj); 20 nmol of [¹⁴C]18:1-TAG added to freeze-dried microsomes in 19 μ l benzene; benzene evaporation, and addition of 100 μ l 0.1 M HEPES buffer (pH 7.0) or 0.1 M HEPES buffer containing 5 mM CaCl₂ or 5 mM MgCl₂; 5 min incubation at 60°C.

Figure S6. The original uncropped version of Figure 2. Immunoblot analysis of oleosin content in total protein extracts of jojoba seeds during germination. M1: oleosins from maize, M2: protein marker.